
LAST MILE LOGISTICS INNOVATIONS; STRATEGIES AND ASSOCIATED COST REDUCTION EFFORTS – A REVIEW OF LITERATURE

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ABSTRACT :

. This paper is inclined to review the recent and past scientific literature contributions on last mile logistics innovations and strategies for cost reduction attainment. Traffics and constructions in urban areas is posing a huge challenge in last mile delivery and causing problems in transport of shipments, especially in freight transport. Meanwhile modern cities need solutions to reduce associated costs like congestion, pollution and others, which have increased in the last few years, especially due to the growth of goods delivery. Online sales and globalization lead to new trends in freight transport, and moreover, a larger quantity of goods is expected to be delivered in the next future. In this context, most of the delivered goods end up in the city centres. Last mile logistics is the least efficient stage of the supply chain and comprises up to 28% of the total delivery cost. Therefore, the improvement of last mile logistics and a significant externalities reduction are very important challenges for researchers. New technologies and transport means, innovative techniques and organizational strategies allow handling in a more effective way the last mile delivery in urban areas. Based on the Systematic Review method, recent papers that significantly contributed, with original proposals, to the reduction of externalities in urban logistics are identified and analyzed in this work. Furthermore, a classification of the papers dealing with the externality reduction problem is presented. It is consistent with a general formulation proposed to evaluate external costs in urban area. The innovative contributions are classified into five main categories: innovative vehicles, proximity stations or points, collaborative and cooperative urban logistics, optimization of transport management and routing, innovations in public policies and infrastructures. The new paradigm of smart logistics is based on the combination of these concepts and on the proposed innovations.

Keywords: *urban logistics; last mile delivery; smart cities; transport externalities; Systematic Review*
